
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ECONOMIC PROCESS MODELING TODAY

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KEYWORDS

Modeling, teaching modeling, economic models, cognitive, heuristic, prognostic, material and technical resources, graphs, schemes

ABSTRACT

The nature, economic necessity, theoretical and methodological foundations of modeling and forecasting in the national economy and its sectors, modeling of socio-economic processes, their economic content, solution by means of modern information technologies, economic interpretation of the obtained results are described. At the same time, in the manual, socio-economic forecasting in the conditions of the market economy is scientific knowledge of the future based on the laws and trends of the economic development of the past and present, and the determination of the goals and tasks of future development.

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IQTISODIY JARAYONLARNI MODELLASHTIRISHNING BUGUNGI KUNDA MUHIM AHAMIYATI

KALIT SO‘ZLAR:

Modellashtirish, modellashtirishni o‘rgatish, iqtisodiy modellar, kognitiv, evristik, prognostik, moddiy-texnik resurslar, grafiklar, sxemalar

ANNOTATSIYA

Milliy iqtisodiyot va uning tarmoqlarida modellashtirish va prognozlashning mohiyati, iqtisodiy zaruriyati, nazariy va uslubiy asoslari, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jarayonlarni modellashtirish, ularning iqtisodiy mazmuni, zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari vositasida echilishi, olingan natijalarni iqtisodiy talqin qilish kabilar bayon etilgan. Shu bilan birga, qo‘llanmada bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy prognozlashtirish - o‘tmish va hozirgi zamonning iqtisodiy rivojlanish qonuniyatlari, tendentsiyalariga asoslangan holda kelajakni oldindan ilmiy bilish va istiqboldagi rivojlanish maqsadlarini va vazifalarini aniqlash.

Model so‘zi lotincha modulus so‘zidan olingan bo‘lib, o‘lchov, me‘yor degan ma‘noni anglatadi.

Iqtisodiy model - iqtisodiy obyektlarning soddalashtirilgan nusxasidir. Modelning hayotiyliigi, modellashtiriladigan obyektga aynan mos kelishi muhim ahamiyatga egadir. Modelda o‘rganilayotgan obyektning hamma tomonini aks ettirish mumkin emas, unda jarayonning eng xarakterli va eng muhim belgilari aks ettiriladi. Shuni unutmaslik kerakki, juda soddalashtirilgan model qo‘yilgan talablarga to‘la javob bermaydiva aksincha, murakkab model esa uni yechish jarayoniga qiyinchiliklar tug‘diradi. Modelning haqiqiyliigi to‘plangan ma‘lumotlar hajmiga, aniqlik darajasiga, tadqiqotchining malakasiga va modellashtirish jarayoniga, aniqlanadigan masalaning xarakteriga bog‘liq. Modellashtirish jarayonining oddiy sxemasi quyidagicha:

- ob‘yekt;
- kuzatuvchi;
- maqsad;
- model;

Hozirgi davrda iqtisodiy ta‘lim sohasida IIJMPning roli tobora ortib bormoqda. Buning sababi ikki tomonlamadir: bir tomondan, tajribaga asoslangan tadqiqotlar usulini chuqur tushuna olishi iqtisodchilarning ta‘lim sohasiga qo‘yilayotgan talablardan asosiysi bo‘lib qolmoqda, ikkinchi tomondan esa matematika va statistikaning iqtisodiy ta‘limdagi roli yanada ortib bormoqda. . IIJMP fanining yuzaga kelishi iqtisodiyotni o‘rganishda bir nechta fanlarni birlashtirgan yondashuv natijasi bilan bog‘liq. Bu fan iqtisodiyot nazariyasi, statistika va matematik usullarni birlashtirish va o‘zaro to‘ldirish natijasida yuzaga kelgan.

Biroq endi faqat matematik statistikaga asoslangan tadqiqot usullari yetarli emasligini hayotning o‘zi ko‘rsatmoqda. Yetuk iqtisodchilar matematik statistika va ehtimollar nazariyasi usullaridan, optimallashtirish va dinamik dasturlash va

matematikaning boshqa usullaridan unumli foydalanganliklari sababli ularning ilmiy salohiyatlari dunyoda tan olingan. Aytib o'tish joizki, Alfred Nobel vasiyat qilgan dastlabki beshta yo'nalish orasida iqtisodiyot yo'nalishi bo'lmagan. Iqtisodiyot bo'yicha Nobel mukofotining rasmiy nomi "Alfred Bernxard Nobel xotirasiga iqtisodiyot sohasidagi mukofot" deb ataladi va u Nobel tug'ilganining 300 yilligi munosabati bilan Shvetsiya Milliy banki tomonidan 1968 yili ta'sis etilgan. Birinchi laureatlar norvegiyalik olim Ragnar Frish va gollandiyalik Yan Tinbergen iqtisodiy jarayonlarni tahlil qilishga matematik usullarni qo'llaganlari uchun bu mukofotni olishga muvaffaq bo'lganlar. Shu paytgacha Nobel mukofoti laureatlari bo'lgan iqtisodchilarning deyarli hammasi ekonometrik tahlil uslublarini iqtisodiy muammoni hal etishda keng qo'llay olganlar. O'zbekiston bozor iqtisodiyotiga o'tish davrini boshidan kechirmokda. Dunyo hamjamiyatida ro'y berayotgan o'zgarishlar bunga ta'sir etmay qola olmaydi. Ma'lumki, iqtisodiyot jamiyat taraqqiyotining asosiy richagidir. Buning uchun kichik va o'rta biznesni rivojlantirishga katta e'tibor berish lozimligi juda ko'p ta'kidlanmokda. Ana shu sohalarni rivojlantirishda esa iktisodchi, menedjer va marketologlarning roli juda katta. Shuning uchun ular o'zgaruvchan bozor iqtisodiyotini tez tahlil qilib, to'g'ri qarorlar qabul qilib, kelajakni prognoz qila bilgan holda yangi yo'nalishlarga tez moslashib ish ko'rishlari kerak bo'ladi. Mamlakatimizning rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyoti uchun nafaqat murakkab ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jarayonlarni tahlil qila oladigan, balki zamonaviy iqtisodiy-matematik usullar va modellar asosida kompyuter texnologiyalarini qo'llab, ushbu jarayonlarni ko'p variantli yechimlarini oladigan iqtisodiy-matematik modellashtirish sohasidagi mutaxassislarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj ortmoqda. Bu esa iqtisodiyotda vujudga kelgan tendensiyalarni, o'rganilayotgan ob'ektlar holatini tadqiq qilishga, ularning rivojlanishini prognozlashga va shu asosda milliy iqtisodiyotdagi chegaralangan resurslardan samarali foydalanish maqsadida ilmiy asoslangan qarorlar qabul qilishga imkon beradi. Bozor iqtisodiyoti murakkab, o'zaro bir-birini taqozo etuvchi jarayonlardan iborat bo'lib, unga noaniqlik va tavakkalchilik elementlari xosdir. Bunday sharoitda iqtisodiy jarayonlarni o'rganishda iqtisodiy-matematik usullar va modellardan foydalanish kutilishi mumkin bo'lgan salbiy hodisalarning oldini olish imkonini beradi. Iqtisodiy-matematik usullar va modellar ilmiy asoslangan qonuniyatlar asosida u yoki bu iqtisodiy jarayonlarning hozirgi holati (statikada), uning istiqboldagi (dinamikada) o'zgarishlarini oldindan ko'rsatib berishga imkoniyat yaratadi. Chunki, bozor kon'yunkturasini oldindan prognozlamasdan turib, korxonalar mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish va sotish strategiyasini belgilay olmaydilar. Bozordagi raqobat kurashi korxonalarga kelajakda o'z mahsulotlarini raqobatbardosh, sifatli va arzon narxlarda ishlab chiqarishni taqozo etadi. IJMP fani orkali milliy iqtisodiyot va uning tarmoqlari kabi murakkab iqtisodiy tizimlarni modellashtirishning nazariy va uslubiy asoslari, aniq iqtisodiy ob'ektlar misolida modellarni yaratilishi, ularning iqtisodiy mazmuni, qo'yilgan masalalarni kompyuter dasturlarida yechish va olingan natijalarni iqtisodiy talqin qilish kabi bosqichlari bilan tanishtiradi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki modellashtirish va prognozlash

(ekonometriya) fanini chuqur o'rganmay turib, uni o'z tadqiqotlarida qo'llay olmay turib, zamonaviy yetuk iqtisodchi bo'lish qiyin. Buning uchun ekonometrik tahlil o'tkazilganidan so'ng olingan natijalarning to'g'ri iqtisodiy talqinini bera olish ham muhimdir.

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